

LANGUAGE BORROWING AND THE INDICES OF ADAPTABILITY AND RECEPTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

One of the most easily observable results of intercultural contact and communication is the set of loanwords that is imported into the vocabulary of each language involved. The field of cultures and languages in contact (Weinreich 1953) has grown a great deal over the past fifty years. From the early studies, a 'Scale' or 'Index of Receptivity' has been posited for languages which more readily accept borrowings. Alongside that scale, a 'Scale of Adaptability' has been posited. The study of a language's adaptability and receptivity of borrowed words, especially those from International English, provides some interesting case studies.

Language Borrowing Processes Language borrowing has been an interest to various fields of linguistics for some time. (Whitney 1875, deSaussure 1915, Sapir 1921, Pedersen 1931, Haugen 1950, Lehmann 1962, Hockett 1979, Anttila 1989) In the study language borrowing, loanwords are only one of the types of borrowings that occur across language boundaries. The speakers of a language have various options when confronted with new items and ideas in another language. Hockett (1958) has organized the options as follows. (1) Loanword Speakers may adopt the item or idea and the source language word for each. The borrowed form is a Loanword. These forms now function in the usual grammatical processes, with nouns taking plural and/or possessive

forms of the new language and with verbs and adjectives receiving native morphemes as well. (2) Loanshift Another process that occurs is that of adapting native words to the new meanings. A good example from the early Christian era in England is Easter, which had earlier been used for a pagan dawn goddess festival. Other Loanshifts in English include God, heaven, and hell. (3) Loan-translation A Loan-translation or Calque occurs when the native language uses an item-for-item native version of the original. "Loanword" itself is a loan-translation of the German lehnwort, marriage of convenience is from the French, and long time no see is a somewhat altered version from the Chinese. An example from the earliest Christian era is gospel, from good (good) and spella (story;

book). The Latin source was related to evangelist (from good plus message plus the ending -ist for person). Good Book and Holy Writ and so on can be seen as loan-translations of the native form godspella or "gospel".

Loan-blend A Loan-blend is a form in which one element is a loanword and the other is a native element, as in the borrowed preost (priest) plus the native -had (hood) in Old English to produce preosthad (priesthood). Each of these four categories is relevant to the overall study of the scale of receptivity, but for the purposes below only the loanword category is relevant.

Loanwords in Language Histories This major section provides an introduction to the study of language borrowings, beginning with a first section giving a brief history of borrowings into the English language. (Whitney 1875, Jespersen 1946, Anttila 1989, Crystal 1995). The following subsections present brief histories of the borrowing history of Spanish, Japanese, and Chinese. The History of English and American English English is one of the world's most prominent languages. Its history is interesting for many reasons, including its flexibility in borrowing from other languages, a flexibility that has enriched its vocabulary over the centuries. Many studies have been done of these foreign elements in English. Jespersen's book (Jespersen 1946) on the history and development of English provided a foundation upon which many others based their own studies of loanwords in English. The history starts Celtic speakers who were conquered by the Romans about a half century BC. Latin was the language of England for centuries until various Germanic tribes – the Angles, Saxons, and

Jutes – began to enter England in some numbers in the 5th century. These Germanic speakers borrowed few of the Celtic words; other Celtic lexical borrowings (also called loanwords or loans) came later, such as: clan, colleen, leprechaun, shillelagh, and slogan. In the earliest centuries "English" was the Germanic language brought over, one which already had identifiable loanwords when it arrived in England. Many Latin words were in the vocabulary, such as wine (L. vinum) and calic (L. calicem, now chalice). The adoption of many words relating to cooking suggests the wholesale adoption of Roman food preparation: cook (L. coquus), kitchen (L. coquina), and foods such as pear, peach, plum, beet, mint, pepper, and so on. The next major influence on English occurred after St. Augustine journeyed to England in 597 AD and Christianized the country. Many Church-related words from the Latin entered the language, some before Augustine but the majority later. Early borrowings included church, minister, devil, and angel. The terminology of the Church system was adopted along with the religion: pope, bishop, priest, monk, nun, Mass, and many more. At the end of the 8th century, Scandinavians ("Vikings") began small raids on England, followed later by colonization. Many place names, personal names, and general vocabulary from Scandinavian languages (Danish, Norwegian) were established during the next centuries. The language borrowings from these speakers are interesting because they are at times borrowings of the "same" word centuries later. [In technical terms these reborrowings are doublets.] For example, Old English scyrte

("shirt") was borrowed as Scandinavian *skyrta* ("skirt"). The two forms came to mean different types of wearing apparel. The next set of invaders was the Normans (French), who represented a more refined culture. From 1066 AD for a few centuries, French became the language of government and of the upper classes in English society. Other than OE king and queen, essentially all current English words related to government are from the French, including govern(ment), reign, country, and state. In terms of social ranking, court titles, and the like, English borrowed most titles: duke, marquis, baron, countess, court, and noble. The advanced military superiority of the French is reflected in the wholesale borrowing of military terms, such as: war, peace, officer, lieutenant, sergeant, soldier, and admiral. Even as Danish law provided some English vocabulary earlier, French control provided several basic legal terms, including court, jury, judge, defendant, and attorney. French, a descendant of Latin, provided another stratum of Latin-derived borrowings in the area of the vocabulary of religion: religion, savior, trinity, angel, saint, and many other related words. A somewhat different and sometimes amusing result is found in the area of food. The lower classes tended the animals, which have their English names: cow, sheep, swine, and deer. As food, the meat appeared on the table of the owner with French names: beef/veal, mutton, pork/bacon, and venison. The upper class English, however, did not use many French words in their written English in the early part of the French occupation. (Jespersen 1946). By Chaucer's time, however, several hundred frequently used words had

entered English vocabulary permanently. Latin, as the language of learning in Europe for many centuries, had an impact during the Renaissance. From the 14th century, Latin, and to a lesser degree, its sister classical language, Greek, have been a continuous source of loanwords. The most obvious places to see Latin borrowings used in English are the terminologies used in biology, botany, and chemistry. The taxonomy and the available compound words are from Latin. Most of the world's scientific community uses Latin as the universal language (or at least terminology) of science. As English traders spread across the globe during the seafaring centuries, thousands of words from world languages were borrowed and became part of the English lexicon. Various dictionaries document the later state of borrowings into the English language. For information on the earlier centuries of English language use, the Oxford English Dictionary (OED) is an invaluable resource. The list below is only suggestive of the paths followed by much of English vocabulary. More examples are given in Appendix A.

Arabic: alcohol, alembic, algebra, algorithm, alkali Chinese: ginseng, japan ("varnish"), ketchup, kowtow German: carouse, cobalt, feldspar, frankfurter, gneiss Italian: artichoke, balcony, bandit, burlesque, casino Japanese: banzai, bushido, geisha, geta, haiku Russian/Slavic: czar, glasnost, intelligentsia, mammoth Spanish: albino, alfalfa, alligator, anchovy, armada

English in North America The growth of American English added words that enriched the lexicon from other sources. Various Native American ("Indian") languages have contributed words, as have

the Black Americans. Native American (various tribes): bayou, caribou, hickory, hogan, hominy, igloo, lagniappe, moccasin, moose, muskrat, opossum, pecan, persimmon Black American: banjo, goober, gorilla, gumbo, jazz, jigger, juke Mexico has contributed not only Spanish words in a variety of meaning areas such as the cattle industry and food, but also words from the native languages of Mexico as well. Mexico has reinforced the Spanish loans and has contributed vocabulary from the indigenous population. Of especial interest are those loans associated with the cattle industry and the Southwest U.S.A. The horsemanship of the early cattle industry was largely learned from the 55 Intercultural Communication .

Mexican experts and the cuisine of the Southwest borrowed most of the items and terminology of Mexican cooking. Mexican: adobe, bronco, burro, canyon, chile, chocolate, cinch, coyote, frijole, hacienda, pinto, pueblo, ocelot, poncho, rodeo, serape, stampede, taco, tamale, tomato, tortilla, vamoose The lexicon of American English contains words that can be traced back to over one hundred languages. Given that speakers from more and more countries are immigrating to the US, many more of the world's languages may contribute loanwords as well. The History of Spanish Spanish is also one of the world's most prominent languages. Its history is interesting as well in terms of language borrowing because of its flexibility in borrowing from other languages, a flexibility that has enriched its lexicon. Many scholars (such as Henríquez Ureña 1938, Santamaría 1942, Spaulding 1965, Lapesa 1968, del Rosario 1970, Lope Blanch 1972, 1979, Zamora Vicente, A.

1979, Cotton and Sharp 1988, Penny 1991) have contributed to the study of Spanish language history. Spanish, like English, is classified as a descendant of Indo-European. An earlier language of Iberia was that of the Ligurians, who preceded the early Iberians and whose language may – as Tacitus suggested – have still been spoken in the first century AD. Some of the early vocabulary may include (Spaulding 1965) forms such as arroyo (stream) and balsa (pond). The Celts had entered Spain by 1000 BC and spread widely. Their presence left words such as briga (eminence) and various place names. Many of the Celtic words were probably carried across Spain by the Romans. The Romans required almost two centuries (201-19 BC) to Romanize the country. The language spoken in Spain was, by the 18th century, mostly from Latin. The framework of Spanish, and a minimum of 60 percent of its vocabulary – if the eighteenth-century estimate of the Benedictine Sarmiento be correct – derives from Latin, not from the pruned and cultivated language of literatures, but from the everyday talk of legionaries, traders, coloni, and the like. (Spaulding 1965, p. 28) In Spanish some Latin words are found that do not appear in the other Romance languages. When used, these words are often considered mere Latinisms. Possibly the situation occurred because the Romans were settling in the Iberian Peninsula approximately a century earlier than in the other countries. Basque, one of the better-known languages at the periphery of Spain, provided a number of loanwords in Spanish, many of which were transmitted through Latin after the Roman conquest. Many of these words are frequently encountered (Penny 1991):

names such as García, Ínigo, Javier, and Sancho, and other words such as boina (beret), chapparo (dwarf oak), izquierdo (left), and zurdo (left-handed). The last major influence on Spanish history and language began in 711 AD when the first Moors (Muslims) landed at Gibraltar. Within seven years they had spread across the peninsula. Over the next seven centuries and more, Arabic was the language of officialdom and religion, but the everyday language remained Spanish. Even so, many Arabic words were introduced into Spanish. Several of the Arabic words (Spaulding 1965) were themselves loanwords into Arabic from Persian, German, and so on. Some examples are:

Guadalajara (Place name)

Zaragoza (Place name - from Latin Caesaraugusta)

alcalde (mayor) aceite (oil) barrio (district of city)

alfalfa (same) adobe (building material) limón (lemon)

Although the Muslims were dominant, the French sent monks to set up monasteries and convents from the early 10th century. With the French came importation both of French words and other Latin words. Latin was placed as the language of learning and the French literary classics were translated into Spanish. French continued to contribute a few words each year for the next many centuries. During the period of Spanish ascendancy in the latter half of the 2nd millennium, the contacts of Spanish with other world languages also provided many loanwords.

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